

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

Research and Innovation action: H2020 – 817626
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Type of action: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Establishment of the stakeholder community

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MILESTONE MS35

Workpackage N°7

Due date: M6

Dissemination level: Public

About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan: i) **Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management;** ii) **Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production;** iii) **Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.**

Project consortium

Part. N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRA Transfert (IT) ****	France

* Universities/veterinary schools

** Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences

*** Public and private advisory services Organisations

**** Knowledge transfer and Innovation organisations

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1 Summary

Stakeholder engagement is managed and carried out under “T7.1 Stakeholders community creation and management”. Under T7.1, the methodological basis for the creation of the Stakeholders Platform covering all the stakeholder community is aimed to be set-up at M6. Prospection for recruitment of stakeholders will be done through different communication channels (in-person/e-mail contact, social networks and project website).

For this purpose, two stakeholder communication channels are created under ROADMAP; a community group on Facebook to initiate discussions, and a repository of documents in the ROADMAP website to share latest developments from the project with stakeholders.

The digital ROADMAP Stakeholder Community group is established and launched in Facebook in November (M6). Facebook has a user-friendly interface giving the opportunity to interact with each other even in different languages through its translation services. This private group aims at attracting different level of stakeholder groups from all over Europe and giving them the floor to shape the project according to the real needs of end-users such as veterinarians and animal health technicians, farm advisors and managers, farmers’ groups and farmers. This ROADMAP Community is the first step in communicating, consulting and knowledge sharing with the stakeholders.

The second step of the ROADMAP Digital Stakeholder Platform consists of the supporting repository of necessary documents in the project website. It is a closed platform (intranet) where the members of SAB and selected international and national stakeholders can reach the confidential documents of the project to get more insight about the project research and results.

This two-level interaction aims to maximise the uptake of the ROADMAP results by different actors in the sector in order to reduce antimicrobial use (AMU).

2 Introduction

The ROADMAP stakeholders are grouped under two categories in ROADMAP. International Stakeholders’ Platform (SP) and Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSCs).

The Stakeholder’s Platform is an international community which consists of Operational and Strategic Committees which feed into the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB). The Operational Committee comprises of farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmers’ organisations and the Strategic Committee comprises of pharmaceutical companies, breeding & feeding industries, retailers & processors, policy makers. The members of the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) are selected from the representatives of different actors.

Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSCs) represent the national stakeholders in partner countries which are initiated and managed by the Country leaders (CLs) or Case-Study Leaders (CSs) and have member of the Living labs. WorkPackage Leaders (WPLs) will also have a technical contribution by feeding the RSCs with inputs and results from ROADMAP’s research activities.

The common contact point for both the international and the national Stakeholder Community is the Digital Stakeholder Platform which facilitates knowledge exchange and exploitation of ROADMAP results.

Figure 1 Structure of ROADMAP Stakeholders

The international advisory board consists of a group of people and organisations representing final users of ROADMAP results (both from the farm level – operational actors – and from the food/drug supply chain level – strategic actors). This group includes external organisations (non-ROADMAP partners) which express a stake or view at a certain moment of the project and are willing to share these with the project partners during stakeholders’ meetings and consultations. They will play a key role in the dissemination and exploitation activities of the project. This group will have a flexible membership and will include representatives from all ROADMAP targeted audiences. Among the stakeholder’s platform members there are three degrees of implication. The first level L1 includes highly involved stakeholders (the Stakeholders Advisory Board – SAB members). They are regularly consulted within the framework of the WPs and case-studies’ activities. A second level of stakeholders L2 includes those actively involved, while the third level L3 is constituted by the final users of the project results.

Figure 2 Structure of ROADMAP International Stakeholders’ Platform

To involve and concretely engage a greater range of stakeholders, ROADMAP will create Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSCs) at national level in all the countries where ROADMAP undertakes research activities. Each RSC will be composed of a balanced representation of the key actors in designated countries and will facilitate dialogue and discussion. Stakeholders that are going to be part of

the RSCs include farmers' and producers' organizations; animal production advisors; veterinary practices and professional organizations; breeding, feeding and pharmaceutical companies; retailers and processors; national public authorities.

Stakeholders will be contacted on how to manage the project issues to maximise outcomes' impacts on AMU reduction and how to exploit the most promising results for transfer by relevant WPs using different methods.

Detailed information on stakeholder engagement in ROADMAP project is given in D7.1 Guidelines for recruitment of stakeholders and D7.3 Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results.

3 Digital Stakeholders' Platform

3.1 Description

The main objective of the Digital Stakeholders' Platform is to facilitate the interaction and communication between different level stakeholders (regional/international, operational/strategic) and between project partners and stakeholders. Digital Stakeholders' Platform consist of two different channels which serve different purposes and are complementary to one another.

3.2 ROADMAP "Stakeholders' Community"

In order to facilitate the discussion between the ROADMAP stakeholders from different partner countries and ROADMAP consortium partners, an interactive private group has been created in Facebook. The reason behind selecting Facebook depends on its user-friendly interface, possibility to discuss in different languages with automatic translation services and that it is widely used by end-users such as farmers, advisors, veterinarians and companies. There are also successful other H2020 communities in Facebook that gather their stakeholders around a Facebook group such as the Disarm Community. There is also link from the ROADMAP official website and GenTORE Stakeholders' Platform.

The Facebook group was launched in November 2019 (M6) and the stakeholders are invited to join in accordance with the D7.1. Facebook ROADMAP Community is managed by EFFAB with support from FEUGA and country leaders.

ROADMAP Stakeholders' Community
Private group

Interacting as yourself

About
Discussion
Members
Events
Photos
Moderate Group
Group Quality

Search this group

Shortcuts
Rotterdam Anneleri
Cagla Yuksel PHOTOG...
Roadmap H2020
GenTORE Stakeholder...
Aqua-Faang Advanci...
Gene-Switch
RA Film Kulübü
EFFAB
Göçmen Anneler™
Rotterdam - Intema...
Hollanda'da Hamileli...
Rotterdam Anneleri Kita...
ROADMAP Stakeholder...

Write Post Photo/Video Live Video More

Write something...

Photo/Video Watch Party Tag Friends

NEW ACTIVITY

Roadmap H2020 updated the description.
Published by Çağla Yüksel Kaya [?] · 1 hr

Welcome to the ROADMAP Stakeholders' Community!
ROADMAP is a project funded by the European Union in order to reduce antimicrobial use in livestock production systems in Europe. ROADMAP aims to make integrated and tailored strategies for the diverse production systems in Europe including pig, poultry, cattle and fish sectors. As ROADMAP team we know we can only make a progress with the actors involved in the production chain and will be the end-users of the strategies we develop.

Seen by 1

Like Comment

Write a comment...

Roadmap H2020 is now linked to ROADMAP Stakeholders' Community.
Published by Çağla Yüksel Kaya [?] · 1 hr

Roadmap H2020
Scientist

3 Likes
1 talking about this

Like Page

Seen by 1

Like Comment

Write a comment...

GROUP BY
Roadmap H2020
3 like this

INVITE MEMBER Embed Invite
Enter name or email address...

MEMBER 7 Members
You have 4 new members this week. Write a post to welcome them.

SUGGESTED MEMBER Hide
Friends
Goksu Ozok Invite Member
Talin Both Kuzuloğlu Invite Member
Cemile Tekin Invite Member
See More

DESCRIPTION Edit
Welcome to the ROADMAP Stakeholders' Community!
ROADMAP is a pro... See More

GROUP TYPE
General

LOCATION
Add Location

CREATE NEW GROUP
Groups make it easier than ever to share with friends, family and teammates.
Create Group

RECENT GROUP PHOTO See All

3.3 ROADMAP “Stakeholders’ Repository”

ROADMAP created a private Stakeholder’s Repository embedded in its public website as an intranet in order to facilitate file sharing. This repository is an online space where an interactive georeferenced map shows the regions covered by the project, and the different stakeholders engaged. This repository is the main tool for stakeholders to stay tuned with the activities carried out by ROADMAP researchers.

Stakeholders can register to the repository intranet directly via the form on the website and they could have access to open information about the interaction with the community. The repository gives permission to documents in different access levels. The group which has access to all documents including confidential ones is the members of the Stakeholder Advisory Board representing the key stakeholders. These members are allowed to comment on the documents, respond to the surveys...etc. Other levels of stakeholders are given the permission to reach to various documents that are targeted for that group. The intranet repository also contain a notification system to alert members by email when a document or event is published or updated. A calendar of events and meetings will also be created as the project progresses and related initiatives will be spread (operational groups, EIP-AGRI events).

It is quite important to add a double consent in the registration form to appear on the stakeholder's platform in order to comply with the GDPR. The stakeholders registered by partners should have given signed consent to the relevant partners.

The intranet repository will be managed by FEUGA with support from EFFAB, country leaders and project management team.

ROADMAP

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ROADMAP STAKEHOLDERS COMMUNITY

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WELCOME

Your platform to contribute, interact and stay tuned to Foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR)

CONTRIBUTE

Submit content via our online form

INTERACT

Connect with other stakeholders on our Facebook groups

STAY TUNED

Subscribe to our newsletter

4 Conclusion

ROADMAP Stakeholders' Community is communicated through ROADMAP website, other social media accounts of ROADMAP, pages of other related project social media accounts and through email. ROADMAP consortium partners and country leaders will be invited to inform and invite their national and international network to the community. Common stakeholders from SAPHIR, PROHEALTH, GenTORE, Disarm and HealthyLivestock projects will also be invited to join the community.

ROADMAP Stakeholders' Community will be the main channel to discuss and consult the ROADMAP stakeholders during the course of the project.